

HOW TO MEASURE FAMILIAL EDUCATIONAL STATUS?

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Abstract:

Familial and educational background significantly impacts an individual's educational, socioeconomic, sociocultural, and sociopolitical progress. Familial educational Status affects the family's educational opportunities and upcoming generations. This creates a need to measure familial educational Status. However, this Measurement is not straightforward and depends on many factors.

This paper proposes three different methods to measure familial educational Status. The first type considers progressive educational level, the second type considers the total time spent on education, and the third type includes multiple educational degrees obtained by the same individual. The findings obtained from these methods can be used to determine the level of educational progress of a family.

This Measurement is essential not only for educational studies, but also for socioeconomic and policy studies. As a result, the analysis of family educational status can be helpful in making socioeconomic policies more effective.

Keywords: *Familial Educational Status (FES), Measurement.*

Introduction:

In every society for which we have data, people's educational achievement is positively correlated with their parents' education or with other indicators of their parents' socioeconomic Status. (Björklund & Salvanes, 2011) Hence, exploring the overall familial educational Status becomes significant. Measuring overall familial educational Status involves many factors, making it more complicated. Different family members have various educational qualifications. Some stop at primary education, while others reach postgraduate or research level. A family's social and cultural background has a significant influence on education. In some families, education is prioritized, while in others, professions or traditional knowledge are more important. Not every family member will necessarily have equal educational opportunities due to differences in educational facilities, economic Status, and gender differences in urban and rural areas. Some families prioritize skill-based education over formal education, making it difficult to compare education. The above reasons make it challenging to measure family

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educational status uniformly. Considering all these challenges, measuring the overall educational Status of anyone's family is complex. However, if only formal education is considered, efforts can be made to measure overall familial educational Status. The procedure is discussed in this paper.

What is Familial Educational Status:

Educational Status generally refers to the level of education completed by an individual. Educational Status examines an individual's level of education or the highest degree or qualification they have attained. However, familial educational Status refers to the overall educational Status of family members. It is the consolidated educational level of all family members.

Why it is necessary to Measure Familial Educational Status:

Educational Status is always the preferred measure of Socioeconomic Status for several reasons. Educational Status is commonly measured by the years spent in the formal educational setup, ranging from pre-primary to Special Higher Education. Levels of schooling are regarded as better indicators of SES. The influence of Parents' education level on familial socioeconomics is directly connected. The parent's educational level and occupation are closely related to living conditions and directly reflect their background and accumulation conditions, so it has significant characteristics and research value. (Zou, 2023) It is an analytical component of SES, indicating the cumulative educational achievements of the family and serving as a substantial predictor of familial socioeconomic development. Family Educational Status dramatically affects an individual's SES. Families with a higher educational status are more likely to provide coming generations with more opportunities, while families with a lower educational status may find the educational journey more challenging. Hence, in human-centric or socioeconomic studies, it becomes significant to explore familial educational Status. In many such investigations, this becomes the most influencing Variable.

How to Measure:

Measuring an individual's educational Status is not a very big deal. In the Indian context, the educational level can be divided into eight categories: Pre Primary, Primary, Upper Primary, Secondary, Higher Secondary, Graduation, Post Graduation, & Special Higher Education (M. Phil, PhD & D. Lit). Considering these categories, the individual educational Status can be identified by a simple question: "What is the educational Level?". However, it becomes a complex situation when it comes to familial educational Status. To take out the consolidated educational Status, one first needs to understand what to consider and what not. Whether we will be considering only progressive education (Progressive education means a step up educational level), or progressive time spent in education (Progressive time spent in education represents a step up educational year) or total time spent in education (Here the total time spent doesn't consider the years spent in education due to the failure in examination but the time

spent in obtaining the equal level of education). Here, efforts have been made to draw up the three different types of measuring familial educational Status.

Type One:

Type one of Measurement considers only progressive education (Progressive education means a step up educational level). In this measurement, a person with equal degrees won't be considered. The measurement technique is mentioned below.

Procedure: The detailed Steps are mentioned below:

Step One: Let's consider the educational levels like Pre Primary, Primary, Upper Primary, Secondary, Higher Secondary, Graduation, Post Graduation, & Special Higher Education (M. Phil, PhD & D. Lit).

Step Two: Assign The scores to these levels: 0) Illiterate, 1) Pre-Primary, 2) Primary, 3) Upper Primary, 4) Secondary, 5) Higher Secondary, 6) Graduation, 7) Post Graduation, & 8) Special Higher Education (M. Phil, PhD & D. Lit)

Step Three: Consider all Family members and know their educational level and the educational level score assigned to them.

Step Four: Consider the aggregate score of all the member's educational levels and divide that total by the total family members considered. The formula is mentioned below.

$$\text{Score Measurement of Overall Familial Educational Status} = \frac{\text{Aggregate score of all the member's educational level}}{\text{Total family members considered}}$$

Step Five: After getting the average score now, calculate the Standard Deviation of the scores received

Step Six: Now the smallest Score is 0 for Pre Primary, and the Highest Score is 8 for Special Higher Education (M. Phil, PhD & D. Lit), and while taking out the average, it is very clear that there will be value in between 0 to 8 means the lower score will indicate the overall weak familia educational status and higher value will indicate the overall strong familial educational Status. On the other hand, standard deviation will indicate the deviation in the value. These average of aggregate scores can be considered independently along with the Standard Deviation or can be divided into categories. Such as Weak Educational status (0 to 2 scores), Average Educational status (3 to 4 scores), Better Educational Status (5 to 6 scores) and Strong Educational status (7 to 8 scores).

Example: A family consisting of 4 members, one of which is educated till graduation, another is educated at a higher secondary level, another is postgraduate, and a fourth one is a graduate. Now, let's consider its scores.

Family Members	Education Level	Scores		d	d2
1	Graduation	6	6-6	0	0
2	Higher Secondary	5	5-6	-1	1
3	Post Graduate	7	7-6	1	1
4	Graduation	6	6-6	0	0
Aggregate Scores		24			2

Divide the Aggregate Scores by Total number of Family Members

$$24/4=6$$

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{\sum d^2}{n}} = \sqrt{\frac{2}{4}} = \sqrt{0.5} = 0.7$$

Now the score to the Measurement is 6 (±0.7) out of the maximum score of 8

The result indicates the overall familial educational Status is 6 (±0.7) out of a maximum score of 8. Or if the categories considered the 6 values fall in Better Educational status (5 to 6 scores).

Type Two:

In type one of Measurement, consider the progressive time spent in education (Progressive time spent in education means a step up educational year). In this measurement, a person with equal degrees won't be considered. The measurement technique is mentioned below.

Procedure: The detailed Steps are mentioned below:

Step One: Let's consider the progressive educational years spent 3 years pre-schooling, 10 years schooling, 2 junior college, 3 to 5 years in graduation, 2 years post-graduation and 2 years in M. Phil, 5 Years in PhD and 5 years for D.Lit. If all these years are considered, then the maximum year spent in the education might be maximum 34 years.

Step Two: Consider the progressive years spent by each family member (e.g., a person studied to 5th standards then has spent 8 years in education, 3 years pre-schooling, and 5 years in schooling).

Step Three: Consider all Family members in the family and calculate the aggregate score.

Step Four: Consider the aggregate score of all the member's educational levels and divide that total by the total family members considered. The formula is mentioned below.

Score Measurement of Overall Familial Educational Status =

$$\frac{\text{Aggregate score of all the member's educational level}}{\text{Total family members considered}}$$

Step Five: In this step, consider mean and standard Deviation. Now, the smallest Score is 0, and the Highest Score is 34, reaching PhD & D. Lit. While taking out the average of, it is very clear that there will be a value in between 0 to 34,

which means the lower score will indicate the overall week familial educational status and higher value will indicate the overall strong familial educational Status. On the other hand, standard deviation will indicate the deviation in the value. These average of aggregate scores can be considered independently along with the Standard Deviation or can be divided into the categories. Such as Week Educational status (0 to 8.5 scores), Average Educational status (8.6 to 17 scores), Better Educational Status (17.1 to 25.5 scores) and Strong Educational status (25.6 to 34 scores).

Example: A family consisting of 4 members, one of which is educated till graduation, another is educated at a higher secondary level, another is postgraduate, and a fourth one is a graduate. Now, let's consider its scores.

Family Members	Education Level	Scores		d	d ²
1	Graduation (Three Years)	18	18-17.75	0.25	0.0625
2	Higher Secondary	15	15-17.75	-2.75	7.5625
3	Post Graduate	20	20-17.75	2.5	6.25
4	Graduation	18	18-17.75	0.25	0.0625
Aggregate Scores		71			13.9375

Divide the Aggregate Scores by Total number of Family Members
 $71/4=17.75$

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{\sum d^2}{n}} = \sqrt{\frac{13.9375}{4}} = \sqrt{3.484375} = 1.866$$

Now, the score for the Measurement is 17.75 (± 1.866) out of the maximum score of 34

The result indicates the overall familial educational Status is 17.75 (± 1.866) out of a maximum score of 34. Or if the categories considered the 17.75 values fall in Better Educational status (17.1 to 25.5 scores).

Type Three:

In type one of Measurement, total time spent in education (Here, the total time spent doesn't consider the years spent in education due to the failure in the examination, but the time spent in obtaining an equal level of education) has been considered. In this measurement, a person with equal degrees will be considered. The measurement technique is mentioned below.

Procedure: The detailed Steps are mentioned below:

Step One: Let's consider the progressive educational years spent 3 years pre-schooling, 10 years schooling, 2 junior college, 3 to 5 years in graduation, 2 years post-graduation and 2 years in M. Phil, 5 Years in PhD and 5 years for D.Lit. If all these years are considered, then the maximum year spent in the education might be maximum 34 years or higher.

Step Two: Consider the total years spent by each of the family members (e.g. a person who studied to graduate twice will have the additional scores for it means if

a person has completed two three-year degrees, the scores for these two degrees will be 6 years).

Step Three: Consider all Family members in the family and calculate the aggregate score.

Step Four: Consider the aggregate score of all the member's educational levels and divide that total by the total family members considered. The formula is mentioned below.

$$\text{Score Measurement of Overall Familial Educational Status} = \frac{\text{Aggregate score of all the member's educational level}}{\text{Total family members considered}}$$

Step Five: In this context, considering mean and standard Deviation Now, the smallest Score is 0, and normally the Highest Score is 34, reaching PhD & D. Lit if equal degrees are not obtained and while taking out the average of it is obvious that, there will be value in between 0 to 34 means the lower score will indicate the overall week familial educational status and higher value will indicate the overall strong familial educational Status an if the score going beyond 34 then it will be considered as Robust / Scholastically Advanced educational status. On the other hand, standard deviation will indicate the deviation in the value. These average of aggregate scores can be considered independently along with the Standard Deviation or can be divided into the categories. Like Week Educational status (0 to 8.5 scores), Average Educational status (8.6 to 17 scores), Better Educational Status (17.1 to 25.5 scores), Strong Educational status (25.6 to 34 scores) and Robust / Scholastically Advanced Educational status (34.1 & Above).

Example: A family consisting of 4 members in which one has completed graduation (Three Years) twice, another is educated at post-graduation twice (Two Years), another is PhD (with three-year graduation), and the fourth one is a PhD. (with a three-year graduation) Now, let's consider its scores.

Family Members	Education Level	Scores		d	d ²
1	Graduation (Three Years/ Twice)	21	21-23.25	-2.25	5.06
2	Post Graduate Twice	22	22-23.25	-1.25	1.56
3	PhD	25	25-23.25	1.75	3.06
4	PhD	25	25-23.25	1.75	3.06
Aggregate Scores		93			12.74

Divide the Aggregate Scores by Total number of Family Members
 $93/4=23.25$

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{\sum d^2}{n}} = \sqrt{\frac{12.74}{4}} = \sqrt{3.185} = 1.79$$

Now, the score for the Measurement is 23.25 (± 1.79) out of the maximum score of 34.1 and above.

The result indicates the overall familial educational Status is 23.25 (± 1.79) out of a maximum score of 34.1 and above. Or if the categories considered the 23.25 values fall in Better Educational status (17.1 to 25.5 scores).

Conclusion:

Measuring familial educational Status is important in socioeconomic studies, as parental education significantly impacts an individual's educational progress, Social status, and Economic Status. This research presents three different methods for measuring familial educational Status:

Type One (Measurement by progressive educational attainment): This is calculated based on the highest educational attainment of family members.

Type Two (Measurement by progressive educational attainment): This is calculated based on members' total years spent in education.

Type Three (Measurement by total educational attainment): This also includes the period spent at the same educational attainment level, thus providing a more accurate picture.

With the help of these three methods, the overall educational Status of the entire family can be understood. The educational attainment score can be used to determine the socioeconomic position of that family. Families with a high familial, educational status provide more opportunities for the next generation, while low educational attainment can create obstacles in the educational process.

Therefore, measuring family educational status is very important for social and economic research and policy-making. Future education policies can be made more balanced and effective by evaluating the impact of education at different levels.

References:

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